

Social Implementation of Tactile Communication in Avatar Robots Operated by Physically Disabled Persons

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Abstract. The COVID-19 pandemic increased the frequency and likelihood of remote interactions, highlighting the importance of physical communication in our lives. In this study, we developed a tactile communication system that transmits haptic information between two operators. We explore the usefulness of the tactile communication system as part of an experiment involving the staff of a cafe where disabled persons who work remotely leverage an avatar robot to serve customers, working alongside in-person colleagues based on the premises.

Keywords: Avatar robot · Physically disabled persons · Tactile communication

1 Introduction

Avatar robots enable remote work or communication by allowing a user to operate a physical agent over a network [1]. For disabled people, robotic avatars represent a new way to participate in society overcoming physical distances and barriers. To date, avatar-mediated communication is mainly audio-visual and does not include the sense of touch, which is central to physical expression, and strongly tied to emotions and interpersonal relationships [2]. At DAWN ver. β , a cafe operated by OryLab Inc., physically disabled people are able to work remotely using OriHime or OriHime-D (OryLab Inc.), an avatar robot that supports communication with customers and the ability to serve food. In this study, we constructed a system that enables tactile communication between remote workers and local staff at the cafe. We explored the application of the tactile communication system and observed how the system is used at the reception desk of the cafe, where a remote worker controls an OriHime-D to take customers' orders and communicate it to in-person staff.

2 System

Fig.1 (a) shows the system. To detect touch input from staff tapping OriHime-D's shoulders, a piezo film (Poly Vinyl dene Fluoride) was attached to both shoulders using

sponges (Fig. 1 (b)). The tactile information was transmitted to the pilot via Zoom (Zoom Video Communications) as stereo input/output to the neck-worn device (Fig. 2 (a)). This allows the correspondence between the left and right sides of the shoulder on which OriHime-D is tapped and the vibration transmitted to the pilot. In return, the pilots used a GUI operation system to send one of four predetermined vibrotactile stimuli. The staff received it with a wireless device shown in Fig. 2 (b). Before experiments, multiple vibrations were collected by using a wearable tactile sensor through texture-rubbing and tapping motions and furthermore created using mathematical formulas. Then, the four stimuli were selected from them through a preliminary experiment using Russell's circle diagram [3].

3 Experiment

One male and two female pilots (52, 41, and 27 years old) participated in the experiment. They had severe disabilities such as quadriplegia or somatoform disorder that made it difficult for them to access work. Our system was deployed from the 16th to the 23rd of January, 2024, during pilots' shifts at the reception of the cafe. The duration of each session was one hour, and the number of sessions for each pilot was respectively four, five, and three. Before the experiment, we instructed the pilot and the staff to decide on the meaning of the vibrations sent from the pilot to the staff. In the first and final trials, pilots performed the task normally without vibrations. After each trial, the IOS [4] on psychological distance and the pilots' work efficiency, reality, and feeling of safety were administered using Likert scales. In addition, we interviewed the pilots and the three cafe staff to gather feedback after the experiment.

Fig. 3. Results of IOS, work efficiency, sense of reality and feeling of safety.

4 Result and Discussion

In this cafe, customers are assigned two areas depending on whether they have, or do not have a reservation. Therefore, two vibrations were primarily utilized for allocating customers into distinct areas. Both pilots and staff said the two vibrations were the easiest to distinguish. Moreover, some individuals employed the other two vibrations during breaks or as signals to let each other know when a customer entered the establishment.

Fig. 3 shows the evaluation results for the pilots, illustrating how the system seems to positively impact all areas. The IOS results indicate that tactile sensation was useful for communication through avatar robots. In the interview, pilots explained how, when communicating with the staff at the reception desk using OriHime-D, they confirmed the response from staff thanks to the vibration generated by being tapped on the shoulder. This in turn seemed to improve the feeling of safety and reality. In addition, some participants said that it was convenient to communicate without words. The results indicate that this system is effective in improving workflow for those who use avatar robots for telework. Also, in the interview with in-person staff, we were explained how the system helped to manage the reception work, and how they also felt that the communication with pilots had improved. On the other hand, some of the staff and the pilots commented that the tactile system reduced the amount of verbal conversation.

This research was initial evaluations, but we plan to conduct longer experiments and more structured evaluations including recording the number of taps on the shoulder and the number of times the vibration is used.

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Disclosure of Interests. K. Yoshifuji is the CVO of the company that owns and operates the cafe, while K. Takeuchi contributes as an engineer. Other authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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